

**THE RESPONSE OF SOME FAMILIES OF GROUND-DWELLING BEETLES TO A
LANDSCAPE MOSAIC IN THE SOUTPANSBERG MOUNTAINS**

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ABSTRACT

Various ground-dwelling invertebrates respond differently to changes in the structure of the landscape. Implementation of a mechanistic approach to landscape ecology is essential to deriving generalizations about how spatial heterogeneity influences ecological system. In the study key questions are asked such as, what is the biodiversity of the area? And what are the threats to biodiversity in the area? We aimed to investigate the response of ground-dwelling insects assemblages to *Eucalyptus* (Bluegum) plantations and Avocado orchards in the western Soutpansberg. We also aimed to develop strategies to maintain, manage and possibly restore the degraded landscapes in the Soutpansberg Mountain using invertebrates as surrogate species to monitor these changes. The study area was Bluegumspoort, the Soutpansberg Limpopo Province, South Africa. Four sites representative of the landscape mosaic were located for the study. The first site located was an Avocado orchard, the second site a Bluegum plantation, third site located was a pristine savanna mist belt and the fourth site a thicket located on Lokovhela. Hand collecting, observations and pitfalls were used to trap and preserve ground-dwelling darkling beetles, (Tenebrionidae), dung beetles (Scarabaeidae), ground beetles (Carabidae) and snout beetles (Curculionidae) at alternating stretches of diurnal and nocturnal sampling. Tenebrionidae constitute the greatest species richness followed by the Scarabaeidae.

Keywords: Tenebrionidae, Scarabaeidae, Carabidae, Curculionidae, insect conservation, landscape mosaic, landscape heterogeneity, bluegum plantation, avocado orchard

INTRODUCTION

Various ground dwelling invertebrates respond differently to changes in the structure of the landscape (Samways 2005). Insects react to these changes at multiple temporal and spatial scales. Insects respond to changes in two ways, firstly, either by adapting to the changes or, secondly, by failing to adapt with consequent local extirpation or regional extinction resulting (Samways, 2005). At the highest scale, individual insects show measurable behavioural responses to changing landscape mosaics (Samways, 2005), as well as responding to fine scale habitat heterogeneity (Barton *et al.*, 2009). For many species one important key to survival is maintaining the connectivity among local populations that allow for dispersal and gene flow between spatially separate patches (Samways, 2005).

Human disturbance remarkably alter the flow of materials, energy and species among different landscape patches (Turner, 1989) and the resulting landscape mosaic is a mixture of natural and remnant anthropologically modified patches that vary in size, shape and arrangement (Turner, 1989). This also influences the diversity of species composition and assemblage structure. The shape and size of the patch can play a major role in determining species diversity and species richness of the particular patch (Pullin, 2002). The theory of island biogeography is often invoked when calculating the size of a patch that can support a particular species at its minimum viable population size. This theory tells us that the larger the size of the patch the greater the species diversity, depending on the habitat quality of the patch (Pullin, 2002) and Samways (2005) found that it was important to identify type aspects such disturbance, genetic drift between habitat patches. Keeping like patches of high quality habitat together in a connective manner enhances not only diversity it maintains gene flow and it also gives us an indication of the intensity at which landscape fragmentation can act on community composition.

Episodic disturbance may change the landscape and these changes in turn influence the spatial and temporal pattern of future disturbance (Forman and Godron, 1986). This view has lead us to the definition of the landscape generated by Forman and Godron (1986) *viz.* the landscape is a heterogeneous land area composed of a cluster of interacting ecosystems or an ecological mosaic. Patterns of biodiversity are influenced by habitat features at multiple spatial scales, yet few studies have used a multi-scale approach to examine ground-dwelling beetle diversity patterns. Habitat can influence the distribution of animal species at multiple spatial scales (Wiens, 1989; Levin, 1992; Gaston, 2000) and it has also been shown that different taxa perceive their environment at different spatial scales (Wiens *et al.* 1997; Manning *et al.* 2004, 2006; González-Megías *et al.* 2007).

As insects are so speciose, abundant and often easy to sample, it is not surprising that they and other arthropods have been widely used for indicating changing ecological conditions (Kremen *et al.*, 1993). For example many studies have shown that particular butterfly species can be used to indicate changes in the landscape because of its vulnerability (McClain and Barry, 2010). Another example would be of the Addo Dung Beetle (*Circulium bacchus*), if they are monitored in the Addo Elephant National Park, their producers of the dung they depend on can be monitored, thus using the dung beetle as surrogates for the African Elephant (*Loxodonta Africana*). This has implication for management in the Addo Elephant National Park. If the dung beetles in the Park are seen to be increasing in number or decreasing, this can tell management whether Elephants in the Park are decreasing or increasing in number. Knowing how the beetles respond to change in the landscape can greatly enhance strategies employed in management of the Addo Elephant Park. And this can be used as environmental surrogates for future management of the reserve.

Studies by Ryke *et al.* (1988) on disturbance showed that large scale disturbance is recognized as a major influence on landscape patterns, yet the impacts of small scale disturbance if often overlooked is not considered at all. Forman and Godron (1986) indicated that landscape dynamics are influenced by complex abiotic and biotic interactions that lead to changes in the structure and function of ecological systems. Disturbance in recent years have shown that they can play a major role in the dynamics of the landscape structure and thus supporting what Ryke *et al.* (1988) have said in their research on the effects of disturbance in the landscape. During agricultural intensification, the overall complexity of the landscape is reduced, natural non-crop habitat is fragmented and the crops/non-crop landscape becomes a mosaic of relatively discrete habitat types (Daily *et al.*, 2001; Tschardt *et al.*, 2002; 2005). Habitat fragmentation is associated with low densities of individual species and high rates of local and regional extinction often through ecological relation, leading to low overall species diversity (Hanski, 1994; Harrison and Bruna, 1999; Tschardt and Brandl, 2004). Individual habitat fragments may become too small to support particular species, and too far apart to be exploited together. Additionally, even if habitat fragments are large enough to support a species in the short term, they may be too far apart to ensure regional persistence through local extinction-colonization dynamics (Hanski, 1994; Hanski and Ovaskainen, 2000).

Within a region, landscapes have attributes that are compositionally and structurally different. Wiens *et al.*, (1997), Kinnunen *et al.*, (2001); Yaacobi *et al.*, (2001) found that beetle species response to habitat change depends on how they interact with their environment. Landscape

heterogeneity is a major structuring agent of ecological assemblages and ultimately contributes to overall higher global diversity (McClain and Barry, 2010). In our study area the area of natural habitats was within a range of 3-5km between sites and the farmland habitats. Studies by Kleijn and Langevelde (2005) showed that distance between natural patches and the farmlands play an important role in insects response to landscape changes.

Most of the landscape offers different elements to the species occurring in it. Not all species will be catered for in the landscape, and some will lack resources to utilize and some conditions to live in. Every species in the landscape has its own way of responding to the global climate change brought upon it. In the agricultural landscapes many ground-dwelling invertebrates depends on patches that are not heavily disturbed or changed in anyway.

Exotic plantations such as Bluegum can greatly change community composition of species as they tend to replace indigenous vegetation. Indigenous ground-dwelling invertebrates depend highly on indigenous plant species for either food or habitat and this is because many insect species have co-evolved with particular plant species. Furthermore change in plant composition might have a negative impact on ground-dwelling beetles causing them to develop other means of survival which to some species might not be possible to adapt quickly to the changes.

The aims of this study were (1) to investigate the response of ground-dwelling beetles in the Soutpansberg due to Bluegum plantations and the Avocado orchards, and (2) to develop strategies to maintain, manage and possibly restore the different landscapes ecosystem in the Soutpansberg. Can changes in the landscape structure actually have an impact on the community composition of ground-dwelling beetles with regard intensive farming and the presence of an alien species invading all sorts of the landscape? The different vegetation type of landscape use is believed to have a significant effect on species richness for beetles. Community composition of beetles might not respond to significant changes in the landscape mosaic, but individual species do.

METHODS

STUDY AREA

The study was conducted in a landscape mosaic consisting of commercial farms such as Avocado orchard and Bluegum plantations, savanna mist belt and a thicket ecosystem in the Soutpansberg, Limpopo Province, South Africa. Non-native bluegum(*Eucalyptus*) tree plantations and avocado orchards have been established in the study area, as a means of commercial farming.

Annual rainfall of the Soutpansberg can reach up to 2000mm (Entabeni) and in other regions of the Soutpansberg rainfall can be as low as 340 mm rainfall peaks during January and February. Mean annual precipitation has been measured at an average of 608 mm per annum and mean annual evaporation been 1678 mm per annum (State of Rivers Report, 2001).

Sites

Four sites were selected *viz.* avocado orchard, bluegum plantation (Figure 1a), savanna ecosystem (Figure 1b) and thicket ecosystem.

Avocado orchard

The orchard is at the edge of the mountain in the southern slopes of the Soutpansberg. The sampling units were placed alongside the avocado trees. The orchard is situated at the foot of the sheer rise. Underneath the canopy of avocados were a dense layer of litter and some grasses of different species.

Bluegum plantation

The plantation is close to the pristine landscape in the mountain and some bluegum trees (*Eucalyptus*) are used as wind brakes in some of the farms in the mountains. The plantation occupies a flat plateau of the mountain and in some part of the mountain bluegum trees are starting to invade the natural landscape due to poor management.

Savanna mist belt

The landscape consists of a continuous structure element of pristine savanna vegetation on top of the mountain with rocky outcrops characterized by high rainfall. The site selected has no disturbance such as farming taking place and is still in its natural state.

Thicket ecosystem

The landscape element is found between the patches of bluegum trees at Lokovhela. In the area the use to be farming in which cattle's use to graze in the area but the sampled site was still in its original form.

Sampling design

We treated each site as a treatment of the land use types in the area, mentioned above. Within each treatment we placed 20 pitfalls in groups of two spaced 10 meters apart. There was therefore 10 sampling units per treatment (or site) spaced 2 meters from each other in order to avoid pseudo replication.

Pitfall traps (Passive collection)

The study took place in the January (2011) to early February (2011) and mid-February (2011) in which pitfall traps were left open for approximately five days before being collected. Each land use had 20 pitfalls in which of the 20 pitfall traps 10 were replicates (sampling units). Thus each site had 20 pitfall traps grouped to make 10 replicates pass. The 20 pitfall traps in each replicate were positioned along trees and was placed 1m apart. Each sampling unit was placed at least 10m away from each other. A crowbar was used to dig holes to place the plastic cups. The plastic cups were dug in so that they would be flush with the soil. In each trap propylene glycol was poured to be used as a preservative agent and to trap the ground-dwelling beetles. Traps were left out for a 5 days. Honey jars were used to store the trapped samples and site names and dates were noted on the cap of the honey jars using a sharp metal pin.

Active collection

Some species of beetles were collected actively during the early mornings and at night. *Night sampling* was performed to trap those individual species that are active during the night and could not be trapped by the pitfall traps that were in place. During active collecting of samples, species were collected from the litter layer on the ground. Sweep nets were used to catch flying invertebrates that also dwell in the ground and at night *light trapping* was used as a passive way of collecting some invertebrates as they come towards the light.

Data analysis

Primer 6 (Clarke and Gorley 2001) was used to analyse differences in beetle community composition in all four habitat. Data imported to Primer 6 (Clarke and Gorley 2001) was square rooted for overall transformation of the data. A species accumulation curve was done in Primer 6 to assess the inventory completeness for beetles in all landscapes sampled. A cluster dendrogram was used to test for differences in community composition among groups. Non metric multidimensional scaling was used to access the dissimilarities and distance among species. With scales Kruskal stress formula: 2 and minimums stress of 0.01. A species list was constructed for all four sites. Histogram and pie- chart were constructed from data on Excel spread sheet, to assess the proportion of morpho-species occurring.

RESULTS

A total of 48 species of beetles were collected during the study. There was a significant different in abundance of beetles in the landscapes. The natural Savanna location constituted most species of beetles (59) and with the least species abundance at the avocado orchard (23). Tenebrionidae family was the major representation of all four families that were sampled with 17 species representing it, Scarabaeidae with 16, Carabidae 11 and the last family Curculionidae with 4 species representing it. This study shows that the assemblage structure of beetles is low in the avocado orchard habitat, which suggests that there might be a biodiversity loss in the avocado orchard. In the study thicket location was found to be the least suitable habitat for most ground-dwelling beetles, with total abundance of 28 individuals and 13 species richness. Avocado orchard and Bluegum plantation yield the same amount of species richness, with Bluegum plantation having the most abundant species 38 between the two landscapes.

Species such as *Anomalipusgonophalum*=01, *Anomalipusstrongylium*=01, *Kheper sp.=02*,*Mausoleopsis sp.=01*, *Scarabaeus sp.8=01*, and Carabidae sp.04=01 were found to be site specific to the avocado orchard;*Scarabaeus sp.7=01*, *Proagoderus sp.=01*, *Copris sp.=01* and Carabidae sp.=3 were only found in Bluegum plantation. Some species of *Zophosis sp.=04* and *Brachycerinae sp.=03* only occurred in natural habitats, where they occurred at the savanna habitat and thicket habitat. The sample based estimators, (species accumulation curve) (Figure 10) which were used (Sobs, Chao 1, Chao 2, Jackknife 1, Jackknife 2, and Michaeliis-Menten) for beetles in the study as a whole. The Chao 2 species richness estimate suggests that sampling was not sufficient enough to generate enough data of species

richness. The inventory completion was highest species richness for beetles in savanna ecosystem. Non-metric multidimensional scaling (Figure 9. circled) suggest that there is no significant difference in species composition between sites except at some point in the thicket site where we see a pattern occurring. The cluster dendrogram showed the relatedness of species occurring within sites (Figure 8. An arrow striking through from one point to another)

DISCUSSION

The data found suggested that more sampling effort has to be employed. The species abundance data also suggest that either the number of pitfalls be increased or sampling should be larger. Some species were seen to be site specific, occurring in natural patches only, and hence the savanna habitat was found to be more species rich and abundance was also high. The different landscapes resulting from different land uses do have a significant impact on species richness and abundance of beetle assemblages. However, beetle communities do not respond significantly to the changing landscape mosaic and this has been indicated in the species composition in thicket habitat and avocado orchard. Changes in the landscape mosaic might not cause ecosystem collapse in the Soutpansberg, but it might as well cause local extirpation of species as some species are site specific which may hinder them from occurring in another habitat in the landscape.

In our study more species were found to occur in the pristine savanna habitat and the species estimate suggested that if more sampling effort is employed and sampling at different seasons might yield a large number of species that inhabit the area (Table 1 and Figure 10). The high abundance and richness of Tenebrionidae and Scarabaeidae in savanna habitat might have been enhanced by animals providing a significant amount of food source for Scarabaeidae spp. as most of them are dung feeders and on the other hand most savanna ecosystems and more region of the Sub-Saharan Africa are predominantly inhabited by dung beetle Tenebrionidae of which they do not need dung for their survival. In our study the tribe Platynotini was highly represented by *Anomalipus spp.* Habitat diversity and enrichment of agro-ecosystem landscapes increases the diversity but it can also reduce diversity as in most agricultural fields insecticides are used to control pest and in turn species might not occur there. Furthermore, Baldock *et al.* (1996) showed that polarization of agricultural practices (in our case avocado orchard and bluegum plantation), from low-intensity systems either to intensification with high material input or to abandonment via marginalization, contributes a threat to biodiversity and how species respond to the changes

occurring in the landscape. And some of the reasons why there seem to be less species in avocado orchard compared to bluegum plantation might be due to: the size of the patch (Figure 3) and habitat heterogeneity and connectivity within the patch (Figure 4) and hence the theory of island biogeography tells us that the larger the size of the patch the more species diversity and abundance.

CONCLUSIONS

The size and activities occurring inside the patch plays an important role in the response of ground-dwelling beetles when the landscapes changes. The data obtained also suggested that before strategies are developed and employed to maintaining the landscape ecosystem of the Soutpansberg Mountains, more sampling effort has to take place and also sampling during different season of the year. Changes in the landscape ecosystems in our have shown that indeed it has impact on how different individual species and communities response and behave when changes are occurring in the area they inhabit. But even that being said our data is not sufficient enough to support this and say indeed the ground-dwelling beetle response negatively to the changes while other species are really doing well regardless of the changes. More sampling and the intensity of the occurring changes have to be looked at in the future as the question still lingers as how do ground-dwelling beetles respond to the changes on the landscape in inhabit and another way would be to use individual species to monitor the changes and behaviour of such species.

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Figure 2 Night sampling with sweep net (Active Collection). Set up of night sampling (Passive Collection).

Figure 3 Picture from Google maps showing site (Avocado orchid)

Figure 4 Google image of Bluegum plantations

Figure 5 Digging pitfalls.

Figures

Figure 6: Histogram showing the proportion of morpho-species between families of beetles.

Figure 7: Pie chart showing percentage of morphological species in their respective families

Table 1. Species inventory completeness for beetles in all four landscapes combined.

	Abundance	Observed species richness
Avocado orchard	23	14
Bluegum Plantation	38	14
Savanna	59	22
Thicket	28	13
All landscapes	148	63

Beetle Data
Group average

Figure 8: Cluster dendrogram of species relatedness.

Figure 10: Species Accumulation Curves showing species estimates.

APPENDIX A

Checklist: Beetles that can be found at the landscapes sampled. Presence absence data.

Family	Morpho-species	Avocado	Bluegum	Savanna	Thicket	
Tenebrionidae	Tenebrionidae sp. 2	0	1	1	0	
	<i>Psammodes sp. 1</i>	0	1	1	1	
	<i>Psammodes sp. 2</i>	0	1	0	1	
	<i>Psammodes sp. 3</i>	0	0	1	0	
	<i>Anomalipus sp. 1</i>	0	0	1	0	
	<i>Anomalipus strongylium</i>	1	0	0	0	
	<i>Anomalipus sp. 3</i>	0	0	1	0	
	<i>Anomalipus sp. 4</i>	0	0	0	1	
	<i>Anomalipus sp. 5</i>	0	0	0	1	
	<i>Gonocephalum</i>	1	0	0	0	
	<i>Anomalipus sp. 7</i>	0	0	1	0	
	<i>Anomalipus sp. 8</i>	1	0	1	0	
	<i>Zophosis sp. 1</i>	0	0	0	1	
	<i>Zophosis sp. 2</i>	0	0	1	1	
	<i>Zophosis sp. 3</i>	0	0	0	1	
	<i>Zophosis sp. 4</i>	0	0	0	1	
	<i>Molurus sp. 1</i>	1	1	1	0	
	Scarabaeidae	Scarabaedae sp. 6	0	0	1	0
		<i>Kheper sp. 1</i>	1	0	0	0
		<i>Scarabaeus sp. 7</i>	0	1	0	0
<i>Scarabaeus sp1</i>		0	0	1	0	
<i>Scarabaeus sp2</i>		0	0	1	0	
<i>Scarabaeus sp3</i>		1	1	1	0	
<i>Scarabaeus sp4</i>		0	0	1	0	
<i>Scarabaeus sp5</i>		0	0	1	0	
<i>Sisyphus sp. 1</i>		0	0	0	1	
<i>Mausoleopsis sp. 1</i>		1	0	0	0	
<i>Scarabaeus sp. 8</i>		1	0	0	0	
<i>Proagoderus sp. 1</i>		0	1	0	0	
<i>Kheper nigroaeneus</i>		0	0	0	1	
<i>Copris sp. 1</i>		0	1	0	0	
Scarabaedae sp. A		0	0	1	0	
Scarabaedae sp. B		0	0	1	0	
Carabidae		Carabidae sp. 1	1	1	0	1
		Carabidae sp. 2	1	1	0	0
		Carabidae sp. 3	1	1	0	0
		<i>Craspedophorus sp. 1</i>	1	1	0	0
	Carabidae sp. 5	0	1	0	0	
	Carabidae sp. 6	1	0	0	0	
	Carabidae sp. 7	1	0	0	0	
	<i>Atractonotus sp. 1</i>	0	0	0	1	
	Carabidae sp. 8	0	1	0	0	
	<i>Atractonotus mulsanti</i>	0	0	1	0	

	Cicindelinae	0	0	1	0
Curculionidae	Brachycerinae sp. 1	0	0	1	0
	Brachycerinae sp. 2	0	0	1	0
	Brachycerinae sp. 3	0	0	0	1
	Brachycerinae sp. 4	0	0	1	0